

the presence of $\nu(\text{C-S})$ (727 cm^{-1} in IIc, 725 cm^{-1} in IIId, 727 cm^{-1} in IIe and IIIf) and absence of $-\text{NH}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bands. However, in these cases, the complexation reaction was found to occur at pH 9.

Electronic spectra of all the above complexes have been determined in visible region and their ν_{max} have been recorded in Table.

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TABLE
ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES OF Cu^{++} , Co^{++} AND Ni^{++} WITH N-BENZOYL-N'-DIMETHYL/DIETHYL THIOCARBAMIDES

S. No.	Metal ion	Name of thiocarbamide & m.p.	Composition of complex	Colour & m.p. of complex	Analytical Data						Wave number ν_{max} cm^{-1}	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
					Found %			Required %				
					N	S	M	N	S	M		
1	Cu^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl- 138°	$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Green 205°	11.80	13.25	13.20	11.74	13.42	13.31	18020	1.93
2	Cu^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-diethyl- 88°	$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Green 115°	10.57	12.02	12.22	10.50	12.00	11.91	17930	1.84
3	Co^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl- 138°	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Bluish Green 155°	11.65	13.35	12.15	11.79	13.47	12.42	16400	2.84
4	Co^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-diethyl- 88°	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Green 70°	10.35	11.72	10.91	10.58	12.10	11.15	16400	2.25
5	Ni^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl- 138°	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Pale Pink 282°	11.50	13.10	12.21	11.79	13.47	12.42	19610	Diamagnetic
6	Ni^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-diethyl- 88°	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Pale Pink 140°	10.49	11.82	11.37	10.58	12.10	11.15	19420	Diamagnetic

The complexes of Copper(II) and Cobalt(II) have been found to be paramagnetic. The complexes of Ni(II) have been observed to be diamagnetic. The magnetic moments of these complexes have been recorded in Table.

Experimental

The metallic salts used in the present studies were of A.R. grade. The required N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl/diethyl thiocarbamides have been prepared according to the earlier described procedure^{6,7}, i.e., by the interaction of benzoyl isothiocyanate and appropriate dialkylamine.

Nitrogen and sulphur estimations of the complexes have been done by Kjeldahl and Messenger method respectively. Composition of the complexes has been determined by conductometric method. Estimation of the metal ion in the complexes has been carried out by the conventional methods⁸. Infrared spectra of the complexes have been recorded employing Carl-Zeiss IR Spectrophotometer, Model UR-10.

Electronic spectra of the complexes have been recorded employing SPEKOL spectrophotometer and solutions were prepared in benzene/chloroform. The magnetic measurements were made at room temperature by the Gouy's method using MnO_2 as the magnetic standard.

Colour, m.p., analytical data etc., of the complexes have been recorded in the Table.

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Synthesis of a few Substituted -3-mercapto-s-triazolo (3, 4-b) benzothiazoles

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CHARLES *et al.*¹ synthesised certain derivatives of 3-mercapto-s-triazolo (3,4-b) benzothiazoles and reported their plant protection activity. Reactions of the 2-hydrazino benzothiazolo with carbon disulphide provided a convenient synthesis² of the above compounds. The 3-mercapto-s-triazolo (3,4-b)

benzothiazole system is also known to possess anti-cancer activity. The preparation and characterization of four derivatives of this system are reported in this communication.

Pharmacology: Preliminary testing has shown that these compounds possess considerable antitumor activity. Details of antitumor activity and other biological activities will be published elsewhere.

Fig. 1.

1) **3-Ethylthio-7-nitro-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole:**

6-Nitro-2-amino benzothiazole was prepared by Hegerschoffs³ method and was converted into nitro-2-chlorobenzothiazole by Sandmayer's reaction^{4,5}. The yield varied from 40–60%. The chlorocompound was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol for 3 to 4 hr. The yellow crystalline compound, 6-nitro-2-hydrazino benzothiazole was separated and recrystallised from 95% ethanol. This compound (4.0 g) was suspended in alcohol (1 : 15) and excess of carbondisulphide added and mixture refluxed for 8 hr. The solution was cooled and the solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. 2.0 g of 7-nitro-3-mercapto-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole was suspended in alcohol. 0.8 g of KOH and 5 ml of ethyl iodide were added. The mixture was refluxed for 45 min, cooled and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated and the residue was recrystallised from alcohol which gave 3-ethylthio-7-nitro (3,4-b) benzothiazole (1.9 g; m.p. 195°–196°). Found: C, 42.64; H, 2.65; C₁₀H₈S₂N₄O₂ requires C, 42.84; H, 2.87%.

2) **3-Ethylthio-7-methoxy-2-phenyl-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole:**

6-Methoxy-2-chlorobenzothiazole was prepared using *p*-anisidine and adopting the procedure given for 6-nitro-2-chloro benzothiazole. 8 g of 2-chloro compound was refluxed with phenyl hydrazine hydrochloride in ethanol for 3 to 4 hr. The colourless compound 2-phenylhydrazino benzothiazole was separated and recrystallised from 95% ethanol. 8 g of this compound was suspended in alcohol (1 : 15), excess of carbon disulphide added and the mixture refluxed for 8 hr. The solid was separated by filtration. 7-Methoxy-3-mercapto-2-phenyl-S-triazole benzothiazole (4 g) was suspended in alcohol, 1.2 g potassium hydroxide and 5 ml of ethyl iodide were added. The mixture was refluxed for 45 min,

cooled and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated and the residue on crystallization gave colourless crystals of 3-ethylthio-7-methoxy-2-phenyl-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole (4.3 g; m.p. 130°). Found: C, 51.50; H, 4.21; C₁₆H₁₆S₂N₃OCl requires C, 51.82; H, 4.06%.

3) **3-Ethylthio-7-chloro-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole:**

This was prepared from 6-chloro-2-hydrazino benzothiazole using the procedure given for the preparation of compound No. 1. It is a colourless crystalline solid, m.p. 195°. Found: C, 44.67; H, 2.61; C₁₀H₈S₂N₃Cl requires C, 44.50; H, 2.98%.

4) **3-Methylthio-7-chloro-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole**

This was prepared following the procedure given for compound No. 1. The 3-mercapto compound was treated with potassium hydroxide and methyl iodide which gave light brown crystalline compound. m.p. 173°. Found: C, 42.10; H, 2.10. C₉H₆S₂N₃Cl requires C, 42.26; H, 2.36%.

The compounds exhibited peaks in the I.R. spectrum at 1410, 3100, 3060, 1600, 1510, 1500 characteristic of S-CH₃ asy. def; CH (aromatic), C=C and C=N respectively. λ Max were observed at 230, 254, 285 and 310 in support of the above conclusions.

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Extraction and direct spectrophotometric determination of palladium with potassium ethyl xanthate

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THE xanthate compounds have been used as reagents for extraction of a number of metals¹. Chakraborty and De² used potassium ethyl xanthate for the extraction of arsenic(III), antimony(III) and bismuth(III). Rao and Sing³ extracted Cu(II),

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